

Conjugation and visualization of *Aiptasia* bacterial isolates with a fluorescence-carrying plasmid

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Summary

Fluorescent labeling of bacterial isolates is a powerful tool to microscopically explore the spatial and temporal dynamics of host bacterial colonization. Bacterial cell labeling has become prevalent in medical and plant research (Gilbertson *et al.*, 2007; Aymanns *et al.*, 2011), but marine host-bacterial dynamics remain largely underexplored. Thus, even though coral microbiome manipulation was shown to effectively improve coral heat stress recovery, the underlying mechanisms remain elusive due to a lack of methods to query bacteria-host and bacteria-bacteria associations. Critical to fully grasp probiotics as an active intervention is an understanding of colonization success, residency, and spatial assemblage of target bacteria. Here, we present a broadly applicable protocol to transform bacterial isolates with fluorescent reporter-carrying plasmids (here: pRL153-GFP) (Tolonen, Liszt and Hess, 2006). Our protocol is based on previous approaches in the freshwater polyp *Hydra* (Wein *et al.*, 2018) and the tubeworm *Hydroides elegans* (Alker *et al.*, 2023). Using this protocol, we successfully conjugated a broad taxonomic range of marine bacterial isolates from the coral model *Aiptasia* using *E. coli* MFD Δ pir Δ DAP WM3064 cells (Ferrières *et al.*, 2010) as plasmid donors. Additionally, we visualized GFP-carrying bacteria in culture and *in hospite* on *Aiptasia* polyps after bacteria incubation. We are currently conducting detailed studies of colonization dynamics and localization of fluorescent bacterial isolates following microbiome manipulation. We hope the here-developed protocol will be useful for researchers studying host-microbiome interactions and the mechanisms underlying microbiome-mediated host resilience.

Step-by-step protocols

Note: The protocols are based on the approaches used by two previous studies (Wein *et al.*, 2018; Alker *et al.*, 2023). Individual steps have been optimized for the conjugation of marine bacterial isolates. To follow the protocols, *E. coli* MFD Δ pir Δ DAP WM3064 cells (Ferrières *et al.*, 2010) and the pRL153-GFP plasmid (Tolonen, Liszt and Hess, 2006) are needed. Both are available upon request.

Figure 1. Overview of conjugation of Aiptasia bacterial isolates with pRL153-GFP using the donor strain *E. coli* MFD Δ pir Δ DAP. First, donor and recipient strains are cultivated, and a common growth medium is selected. Chemically competent donor cells are transformed with the pRL153-GFP plasmid, and a minimal inhibitory kanamycin concentration is determined for each recipient strain. Once these steps are completed, recipient cells are conjugated with pRL153-GFP using the transformed donor cells. Lastly, Aiptasia polyps are incubated with successfully conjugated green fluorescent recipient cells for visualization *in hospite*.

1. Maintenance of donor and recipient strains

Note: Donor cells are *E. coli* MFD_{pir} ΔDAP WM3064 (Ferrières *et al.*, 2010; Wein *et al.*, 2018). Donor cell growth medium needs to be supplemented with 0.1 mM diaminopimelic acid (DAP) to ensure efficient growth. Recipient cells are pure cultures of bacterial isolates from Aiptasia strains F003 (Grawunder *et al.*, 2015) and H2 (Xiang *et al.*, 2013). The taxonomic identity of all strains was verified via 16S rRNA gene Sanger sequencing prior to the experiments.

Donor cell maintenance:

1. Prepare 60 nM diaminopimelic acid (DAP) stock solution:
 - a. Dissolve 114 mg DAP in 10 mL VE water.
 - b. Stir on a magnetic stirrer for 10 min.
 - c. Once fully dissolved, filter sterilize (0.2 μm filter) into a sterile 25 mL Falcon tube.
 - d. Store at room temperature (RT) wrapped in aluminum foil to shield from light.
2. Prepare LB medium and agar plates supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP. Add DAP only after the medium or agar has cooled down to 50 °C after sterile autoclaving.
3. To establish stable growth of donor cells, streak *E. coli* MFD_{pir} ΔDAP donor cells once a week on fresh LB agar plates supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP.
4. Incubate at 37 °C until single colonies are forming (usually overnight) and move the agar plates to a fridge for short-term storage.

Recipient cell maintenance:

1. Prepare appropriate growth media and agar plates for recipient cells (Aiptasia bacterial isolates), e.g., Marine agar, Blood agar, etc. (Sweet *et al.*, 2021; Rodrigues and de Carvalho, 2022).
2. To establish stable growth of recipient cells, streak bacterial isolates once every one or two weeks, depending on the growth rate of the individual isolates.
3. Incubate at an appropriate growth temperature (e.g., 25 °C – 28 °C) until single colonies form. Move the agar plates to an incubator at 18 °C for short-term storage.

Note: Be aware that marine bacteria tend to grow slowly and might require anything from 24 h up to multiple days for proper growth.

2. Selection of common growth medium for donor and recipient strains

Note: To ensure conjugation success, donor and recipient cells need to grow efficiently on a common growth medium. As a starting point, it is easiest to test whether the donor strain can grow in the recipient cell growth media.

1. Prepare recipient and donor cell growth media and agar plates supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP.
2. For a simple liquid culture growth test, prepare liquid mini cultures of the recipient and donor (positive control) cell growth medium supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP in triplicates.
3. Inoculate each liquid culture with one colony of the donor *E. coli* MFD*pir* Δ DAP.
4. Incubate the liquid cultures overnight at 37 °C with 180 rpm.
5. Verify visible growth and measure cell density via OD_{600nm} measurements (using a photometer or microplate reader) and compare donor cell growth in recipient cell growth media to the positive control.
6. An agar growth test can be performed by streaking one colony of the donor *E. coli* MFD*pir* Δ DAP each on recipient and donor (positive control) cell growth agar plates.
7. Incubate at 37 °C overnight or until single colonies form.
8. Compare the cell growth of donor cells on the recipient cell growth agar plates to the positive control agar plates.

3. Transformation of donor cells with the fluorescence-carrying plasmid

Note: The plasmid pRL153-GFP (Tolonen, Liszt and Hess, 2006; Wein *et al.*, 2018) needs to be transformed into the donor strain *E. coli* MFD*pir* Δ DAP prior to conjugation with Aiptasia bacterial isolate recipient cells. The plasmid carries a kanamycin resistance gene; thus, the selection of positive clones is achieved with 25 µg/mL kanamycin.

1. Prepare chemically competent *E. coli* MFD*pir* Δ DAP donor cells following established protocols using CaCl₂ treatment (e.g., Chang *et al.*, 2017).
2. Prepare LB medium supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP and LB agar plates supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP and 25 µg/mL kanamycin.
3. Set a heating block to 42 °C, pre-warm 1 mL LB medium supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP and LB agar plates supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP and 25 µg/mL kanamycin to 37 °C.
4. Thaw an aliquot of chemically competent *E. coli* MFD*pir* Δ DAP donor cells on ice.
5. Carefully add 5 – 100 ng pRL153-GFP plasmid and gently mix without pipetting up and down.
6. Incubate the transformation solution on ice for exactly 30 min.
7. Transfer the transformation solution to the heat-block pre-warmed to 42 °C and heat-shock for exactly 30 sec.
8. Immediately incubate the transformation solution on ice for 5 min.
9. Add the pre-warmed 1 mL LB medium supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP and grow the bacteria for ~ 1 h at 37 °C with 180 rpm.
10. Plate 100 – 200 µL on pre-warmed LB agar plates supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP and 25 µg/mL kanamycin.
11. Incubate at 37 °C overnight or until single colonies form.

12. To verify transformation and select positive clones, perform a colony PCR (Bergkessel and Guthrie, 2013) for the GFP gene encoded on pRL153-GFP using multiple transformed *E. coli* MFD*pir* ΔDAP colonies growing on the selective LB agar plates. Prepare a colony PCR master mix as follows:

Reagent	Volumes in μL for one reaction
QIAGEN Multiplex PCR master mix (100) (Cat. No. / ID: 206143)	5
Forward primer pRL153_seq_fw (10 μM) (5' CGGCTCGTATAATGTGTGGAATTG 3')	0.5
Reverse primer pRL153_MSC_seq_rev (10 μM) (5' CTATCAGATCAGCATTCCGC 3')	0.5
Molecular Biology Grade Water	4

13. Transfer 10 μL of the PCR master mix into PCR tubes while keeping the mix on ice.
14. Pick the respective transformed *E. coli* MFD*pir* ΔDAP colonies directly into the PCR master mix, swirl them briefly, and streak them on a colony PCR master agar plate (LB agar plate supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP and 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ kanamycin).
Note: Make sure to not pick up agar when picking the bacteria because residual agar could decrease PCR amplification efficiency.
 Incubate the colony PCR master agar plate at 37 °C overnight or until single colonies form.
Note: Bacteria are streaked from the selection agar plate to a fresh colony PCR master agar plate to ensure continuous growth of the bacteria tested. It is helpful to label each colony tested and to draw a grid on the colony PCR master agar plate with respective labels to keep track of each colony.
15. Place the PCR tubes in a PCR thermocycler using the following PCR program:
- | | | |
|------------------|------------------|-------------|
| Bacterial lysis: | 95 °C for 15 min | |
| Denaturation: | 95 °C for 30 sec | |
| Amplification: | 57 °C for 30 sec | x 30 cycles |
| Extension: | 72 °C for 60 sec | |
| Final extension: | 72 °C for 10 min | |
| Final hold: | 8 °C (forever) | |
16. Verify successful PCR amplification of the GFP insert via 1 % gel electrophoresis. The expected amplicon size is 1045 bp.
17. To store the transformed bacteria, inoculate a liquid culture of positively selected clones using LB medium supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP and 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ Kanamycin, prepare glycerol cryopreservation stocks with a final concentration of 20 % glycerol, and store the samples at -80 °C.
Note: Plasmids are stably retained in *E. coli* MFD*pir* ΔDAP donor cells if kept as cryopreservation stocks. However, it is recommended to verify plasmid presence after revival via colony PCR for the GFP gene before continuing with downstream experiments.

4. Determination of the minimal inhibitory antibiotic concentration (MIC) of recipient strains

Note: The minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) of a suitable antibiotic needs to be determined for each recipient strain to ensure successful transconjugant selection following conjugation. Here, we use kanamycin to determine the MIC of each recipient strain, as pRL153-GFP carries a kanamycin resistance gene. Our protocol for MIC testing is based on two previous studies (Wiegand, Hilpert and Hancock, 2008; Alker *et al.*, 2023).

1. Prepare agar plates with gradual concentrations of kanamycin using an appropriate recipient cell growth medium. Let the agar cool down to 50 °C after sterile autoclaving before adding kanamycin (stock solution: 50 mg/mL; concentrations used for MIC testing: 400 µg/mL, 300 µg/mL, 200 µg/mL, 100 µg/mL, 50 µg/mL and 25 µg/mL). Prepare agar plates without kanamycin to use as a positive growth control.
2. Prepare a liquid culture of each recipient bacterial isolate in 3 mL of recipient cell growth medium. Incubate at an appropriate growth temperature (e.g., 25 °C - 28 °C) until the cultures reach an optical density (OD_{600nm}) corresponding to 10⁷ - 10⁸ cells/mL.
Note: An optical density value (OD_{600nm}) corresponding to 10⁷ - 10⁸ cells/mL can be determined via colony forming unit (CFU) counts using standardized protocols (e.g., Jett *et al.*, 1997).
3. Bring the cultures to a concentration of 10⁷ cells/mL (dilute with growth medium, if needed).
4. Spot-inoculate 1 µL of the liquid recipient cell culture on pre-warmed agar plates supplemented with your antibiotic of choice for MIC testing spots containing 10⁴ bacteria cells. Spot-inoculate 6 spots per recipient strain per antibiotic concentration. Spot-inoculate 6 spots per recipient strain on agar plates without antibiotics as a positive growth control.
Note: Vortex the recipient cell solution in between each spot-inoculation.
5. Incubate the agar plates for at least 24 hours at an appropriate growth temperature (e.g., 25 °C - 28 °C) or until bacterial growth is visible on the growth control agar plates.
6. Compare bacterial growth between agar plates with increasing antibiotic concentrations. The first agar plate where no bacterial growth is visible determines the MIC (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Determination of the minimal inhibitory antibiotic (here: kanamycin) concentration for Aiptasia bacterial isolate recipient strains. Agar plates with gradual kanamycin concentrations were spot inoculated with 10^4 cells/spot (= 1 μ L/spot). A plate with 0 μ g/mL kanamycin was prepared as a growth control. After incubation at an appropriate growth temperature for at least 24 h, the first agar plate without visible growth determined the MIC.

5. Conjugation of donor and recipient strains

Note: The conjugation protocol is based on protocols published by Wein *et al.*, 2018 and Alker *et al.*, 2023 with optimizations from our side.

1. Prepare agar growth plates and growth media as follows:
 - a. LB agar and medium supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP and 25 µg/mL kanamycin (to cultivate the donor strain *E. coli* MFD*pir* ΔDAP-GFP).
 - b. Respective recipient cell growth agar and medium (without DAP or antibiotics, to cultivate the recipient strain).
 - c. Recipient cell growth agar supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP (to plate the conjugation mix of donor and recipient cells).
 - d. Recipient cell growth agar supplement with a suitable antibiotic concentration according to previously determined MIC values (to cultivate transconjugant recipient cells).
2. Prepare a pre-culture of the plasmid-carrying donor strain *E. coli* MFD*pir* ΔDAP-GFP using LB agar supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP and 25 µg/mL kanamycin.
3. Prepare pre-cultures of the recipient strains using respective recipient cell growth agar.
4. Inoculate a 3 mL liquid culture of the donor strain *E. coli* MFD*pir* ΔDAP-GFP using LB broth supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP and 25 µg/mL kanamycin and incubate the culture at 37 °C overnight until shortly before the cells reach the stationary growth phase (usually after around 16 h; OD_{600nm} = 0.6 – 0.8).
5. Inoculate a 3 mL liquid culture of the recipient strains using respective recipient cell growth media. Incubate at an appropriate growth temperature (e.g., 25 – 28 °C) until they reach the stationary phase (24 – 48 h depending on the isolate, OD_{600nm} = 0.6 – 0.8).
6. Harvest 3 mL donor and recipient cell cultures at 1:1 OD_{600nm} ratio at 4000 x g for 3 min.
7. Remove all supernatant from the recipient cells and resuspend the cell pellet in 100 µL recipient cell growth medium.
8. Remove all supernatant from the donor cells.
9. Transfer the 100 µL resuspended recipient cells to the donor cells and resuspend the donor cells very carefully.
10. Spot-inoculate two 50 µL spots on pre-warmed agar plates of an appropriate recipient cell growth medium supplemented with 0.1 mM DAP (without antibiotics!).
11. Incubate the cells at an appropriate cell growth temperature (e.g., 25 °C – 28 °C) for 16 – 24 h leaving the agar plates unsealed with the lids facing up.

Note: The conjugation between donor and recipient cells occurs on the agar plate during the incubation period.
12. The next day, scrape up the cells from the agar plate using a scraper (e.g., the blunt end of a scalpel or a sterile spatula) without scraping up agar and resuspend the cells in 500 µL of recipient cell growth medium (without DAP and without antibiotics).
13. Plate 100 µL of the conjugation cell mixture on recipient cell growth agar supplemented with a suitable concentration of antibiotic (according to the previously determined MIC value of the respective recipient strain).

Note: *E. coli* MFD*pir* ΔDAP-GFP donor cells should perish due to the lack of DAP. Only positive recipient transconjugants should survive and grow efficiently due to the antibiotic selection pressure.

14. Incubate the agar plates at an appropriate cell growth temperature (e.g., 25 – 28 °C) for 24 – 48 h.
15. Pick single colonies from the agar plate and transfer them to fresh recipient cell growth agar plates supplemented with a suitable antibiotic concentration (Figure 3).
Note: This process can be repeated 2-3 times before continuing with conjugation verification (see troubleshooting notes).
16. Continue with colony PCR to verify the presence of the pRL153-GFP plasmid in the recipient cells, as detailed in section 3, steps 12-16. Use recipient cell growth agar supplemented with a suitable concentration of antibiotic as the colony PCR master agar plates.
17. To verify the correct taxonomic identification of the conjugated recipient cell, perform a 16S rRNA gene colony PCR on the same colonies that were tested for the presence of pRL153-GFP. Perform colony PCR as described in section 3, steps 12-16, using the following primer pair (Lane *et al.*, 1991):
 Forward primer (27F wobble): 5'-AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG-3'
 Reverse primer (1492R): 5'-GGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3'
 Use the following PCR cycling protocol:
 Bacterial lysis: 95 °C for 15 min
 Denaturation: 95 °C for 30 sec |
 Amplification: 55 °C for 30 sec | x 30 cycles
 Extension: 72 °C for 60 sec |
 Final extension: 72 °C for 10 min
 Final hold: 8 °C (forever)
 Use recipient cell growth agar supplemented with a suitable concentration of antibiotic as the colony PCR master agar plates.
18. Verify successful PCR amplification of the 16S rRNA gene via 1 % gel electrophoresis. The expected amplicon size is around 1500 bp.
19. Prepare the PCR product for Sanger sequencing using your PCR clean-up kit of choice (e.g., ExoProStar 1-Step, [link](#)) and use the 16S rRNA gene colony PCR primer pair (27F wobble and 1492R) for the sequencing reaction. Map your sequencing results to a reference sequence of the respective recipient strain and verify correct taxonomic identification.
20. To store the conjugated recipient cells, inoculate a liquid culture of positively selected clones using recipient cell growth medium supplemented with the appropriate antibiotic concentration, prepare glycerol cryopreservation stocks with a final concentration of 20 % glycerol and store the samples at -80 °C.

Notes on troubleshooting:

1. Marine bacteria might take longer to grow. In this case, larger culture volumes can be prepared and harvested to reach a 1:1 donor-to-host cell ratio.
2. Experience has shown that the donor strain *E. coli* MFD*pir* ΔDAP-GFP either does not immediately perish under lack of DAP or dead cells can be accidentally picked up for colony PCR, both leading to misleading 16S rRNA gene sequencing results. To improve sequencing results, colonies can be passaged twice on fresh agar plates (instead of once) before colony PCR and 16S rRNA gene sequencing are attempted.

Figure 3. Conjugation of donor *E. coli* MFDpir Δ DAP-GFP and recipient *Aiptasia* bacterial isolate cells. Donor and recipient cells are cultivated and harvested at a 1:1 OD_{600nm} ratio. Cells are resuspended and mixed before spot-inoculation on recipient growth agar plates. Cells are then transferred to selective recipient growth agar plates lacking DAP but containing a suitable antibiotic concentration (here, Kan = kanamycin). Lastly, single colonies are transferred to fresh selective agar plates, and conjugation is verified via 16S rRNA gene and GFP gene colony PCR.

6. Visualization of fluorescent recipient strains

Note: After successful conjugation, fluorescent bacterial isolates were imaged in culture and *in hospite* on *Aiptasia* polyps. You can use any fluorescent microscope of your choice for imaging. In this case, the Axioscope 40 (Zeiss) was used, and images were taken using AxioCam 305 color and Zeiss ZEN 3.3 imaging software.

1. Revive a conjugated bacterial isolate from a cryopreservation stock by passaging twice on suitable cell growth agar plates supplemented with an appropriate antibiotic concentration.
2. Inoculate 3 mL liquid culture using a suitable cell growth medium supplemented with an appropriate antibiotic concentration and incubate the cultures at a suitable cell growth temperature for at least 24 h.
3. Measure the bacterial density (OD_{600nm}) of the liquid culture and dilute the culture to a density equal to 10^8 cells/mL (see section 4, step 2 for details).
4. To image bacteria in growth medium, simply transfer 1 μ L bacteria solution to a microscopy slide and add a coverslip. Carefully press down on the coverslip to spread the cellular solution as much as possible. Seal the corners with nail polish (optional).
5. To immobilize bacteria prior to imaging, harvest some bacteria (e.g., 90 μ L) at 10,000 x g for 2 min. Remove the supernatant and replace it with the same volume of 80 % glycerol (e.g., 90 μ L). Carefully resuspend the bacterial pellet and prepare a microscopy slide with 2 μ L bacteria solution.
6. Image the bacteria using an oil-immersion 100x objective and Alexa-488 filter.
7. Use an imaging software such as FIJI ([link](#)) (here, version 2.14.0/1.54f) to process the images (Figure 4).

M. adhaerens-GFP

Figure 4: Visualization of fluorescent *Aiptasia* bacterial isolates in culture. *Marinobacter adhaerens* was successfully conjugated with pRL153-GFP and a liquid culture of 10^8 cells/mL was visualized using a fluorescent microscope and Alexa-488 filter. Representative fluorescent microscopy images of (A) *M. adhaerens* liquid culture in growth medium and (B) *M. adhaerens* liquid culture immobilized in 80% glycerol. 100x objective, scalebar = 10 μ m.

8. To prepare bacteria solutions for inoculation of *Aiptasia* anemones, use 5 mL bacterial isolate culture at 10^8 cells/mL and harvest the cells at 3,000 x g for 5 min.
9. Remove the supernatant, add 5 mL filtered artificial sea water (FASW), and resuspend the bacterial pellet.
10. In a 6-well plate, add 5 mL bacteria in FASW to a well and add five small *Aiptasia* polyps. Add five small *Aiptasia* polyps in FASW without bacteria to another well as a negative control.
11. Incubate overnight under *Aiptasia* culturing conditions (26 °C, 12 h light, 12 h dark).
12. Wash the polyps once with fresh FASW and transfer them to a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube with 80 % glycerol.
13. To image *Aiptasia* polyps with fluorescent bacteria, add a polyp with as little glycerol as possible to a microscopy slide. Add a cover glass and press down on the polyp to spread the tissue.
14. Proceed with imaging as detailed above and process images using an imaging software such as FIJI ([link](#)) (Figure 5).

H2 *Aiptasia* inoculated with *M. adhaerens*-GFP (10^8 cells/mL)

Figure 5: Visualization of fluorescent *Aiptasia* bacterial isolates *in hospite*. *Aiptasia* anemones (strain H2) were inoculated with fluorescent *M. adhaerens* bacteria (10^8 cells/mL) for 24 h prior to imaging using a fluorescent microscope and Alexa-488 filter. Fluorescent *M. adhaerens* bacteria are present on the host tissue (white arrowheads). *Aiptasia* symbiont autofluorescence is detected as well (asterisks). Representative fluorescent microscopy images of (A) brightfield, (B) GFP (Alexa-488) filter, (C) and merged *Aiptasia* tissue with fluorescent *M. adhaerens*.

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